

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AS RELATED TO PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Education as an organization is no exception, because it is also a demanding profession; and the success and achievement of educational goals also depend on the highly dedicated and committed teachers. Teacher Commitment is crucial to effective teaching, teacher satisfaction, and retention. The present study deals with the inter correlation between four dimensions of psychological capital and three dimensions of organizational commitment. In the present study data were collected from 400 secondary school teachers out of which 200 were males and 200 were females. The data was analysed by Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient. This paper confirms that impacts of PsyCap as antecedents of organizational commitment are almost similar to those in other organizational setups and work places. Implicitly, it implies that the school education system is bearing the common structural and functional features with other organizations, and human resource characteristics are equally important in effectiveness of educational organizations. Findings of the present study have depicted the significant positive relationship between psychological capital and organizational commitment. It is well established that psychological capital is developmental, so it implies that developing psychological capital, organizational commitment can be enhanced and surely useful for teachers.

Key Words: Organizational Commitment, Psychological Capital & Secondary School Teachers

Introduction:

Education as an organization is no exception, because it is also a demanding profession; and the success and achievement of educational goals also depend on the highly dedicated and committed teachers. Teacher Commitment is crucial to effective teaching, teacher satisfaction, and retention (Fresko et al, 1997; Singh and Billingsley, 1998; Joffres and Haughey, 2001; Wang and Hwang, 2007; Sharma, 2008a, 2008b; Aydin et al, 2011; Gupta and Gehlawat, 2013; Sharifi and Shahtalebi, 2014; Beri and Beri, 2014; Arogundade et al, 2015; Khan, 2015). Researchers have revealed that low level of teacher commitment may result in decreased academic achievement of students, higher teacher absenteeism, increased staff turnover, and decline in educational standards (Kushman, 1992; Reyes and Fuller 1995; Joffres and Haughey, 2001; Dee et al, 2006). So, fostering commitment among teachers and other academic staff is important because, as mentioned in literature, highly committed employees stay longer, perform better, miss less work, and more engage in organizational citizenship behaviour. Literature reveals all the three components of Organizational Commitment to be positively correlated with each other. It also reveals that relationship between Affective Commitment and Normative Commitment is somewhat high or than with Continuance Commitment. The low relationship of Continuance Commitment with Affective Commitment and Normative Commitment is related to the age and experiences. Young employees usually remain deficient or low in continuance commitment (Finegold et al, 2002). Luthans et al., (2008) conducted a study to investigate the mediating role of psychological capital in the supportive organizational climate and employee performance. The study was conducted to check whether the variables of positive psychological capital i.e. hope, resilience, optimism, and efficacy played a role in mediating the effects of a supportive organizational climate with employee outcomes. Sharifi and Shahtalebi (2014) studied the relationship between dimensions of psychological capital with organizational commitment on staff of Isfahan. The descriptive survey method was used to investigate the relationship between the dimensions of psychological capital and of organizational commitment. The present study was mainly designed to examine the extent of relationship between the organizational commitment and psychological capital among secondary school teachers.

Objectives:

- To study the relationship between various dimensions of organizational commitment.
- To study the relationship between various dimensions of psychological capital
- To study the inter correlation between four dimensions of psychological capital and three dimensions of organizational commitment.

Hypothesis:

- Three components of organizational commitment are correlated positively to each other.
- Three components of Psychological Capital are correlated positively to each other.

- Variables of Psychological Capital (hope, optimism, resilience, self-efficacy) are likely to correlate positively with organizational commitment.

Method:

The present study was planned to study inter correlation between organizational commitment and psychological capital of Secondary School teachers. To realize the main objective of the study, 400 Secondary School teachers were randomly selected from the various schools of Haryana; and were tested with Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (Mayers and Allens, 1990) and Psychological Capital Scale (Luthans et al, 2007)

Sample:

Four hundred Secondary School teachers from various Government and Private Secondary Schools of four districts - Sonapat, Karnal, Panipat and Rohtak of Haryana were randomly selected to participate in the present study. The four hundred subjects consisted of 200 males (100 Government and 100 Private school teachers) and 200 females (100 Government and 100 Private school teachers) whose data protocols have been used in the present study.

Tests / Measures:

Following tests / measures were used in the present study for data collection

- Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (Meyers and Allens, 1990)
- Psychological Capital Questionnaire (Luthans et al, 2007)

Results and Discussions:

Obtained data was analysed by using descriptive statistics to ascertain normalcy of data, t-ratio to examine the significance difference in the mean scores and Pearson's Correlations to ascertain the degree of relationship between four factors of Psychological Capital and three of Organizational Commitment.

Table 1: Inter Correlations Matrix (Males)

After ascertaining that obtained data meet the requirement of application of Product Moment Method of Correlation, Correlations were obtained through SPSS among all the measures used in the study from the raw scores of 200 male Secondary School teachers and are reported in Table 1.

	Hope	Efficacy	Resilience	Optimism	AC	NC	CC
Hope	XX						
Efficacy	0.476	XX					
Resilience	0.315	0.423	XX				
Optimism	0.496	0.557	0.404	XX			
AC	0.38	0.347	0.223	0.348	XX		
NC	0.406	0.29	0.327	0.379	0.59	XX	
CC	0.265	0.251	0.277	0.209	0.416	0.505	XX

Degree of Freedom being 198 (N-2), the correlation coefficients of .138 and .181 are significant at .05 and .01 probability levels. Obtained correlations are reported in the following sub sections.

- Correlations among four measures of Psychological Capital are in general positive ranging from .315 to .557 with all being significant. Hope has correlated positively with Self- Efficacy ($r = .476, p < .01$), Resilience ($r = .315, p < .01$), and Optimism ($r = .496, p < .01$). Self-Efficacy has marked significant positive relationship with Resilience ($r = .423, p < .01$) and Optimism ($r = .557, p < .01$). Resilience has correlated positively with Optimism ($r = .404, p < .01$). Obtained correlations depict that four measures of PsyCap have shared substantial amount of variance among them and the construct validity of Ps Cap Questionnaire.
- Correlations between two types of measures are in general positive ranging from .209 to .406 with all the 12 being significant. Affective Commitment has correlated positively with Hope (.380, $p < .01$), Self-efficacy (.347, $p < .01$), Resilience (.223, $p < .01$) and Optimism (.348, $p < .01$). Normative Commitment has marked significant positive relationship with Hope (.406, $p < .01$), Self-efficacy (.290, $p < .01$), Resilience (.327, $p < .01$) and Optimism (.379, $p < .01$). Continuance Commitment has marked significant positive association with Hope (.265, $p < .01$), Self-efficacy (.251, $p < .01$), Resilience (.277, $p < .01$) and Optimism (.209, $p < .01$). Obtained Correlations hereby depict that two types of measures have shared substantial amount of variance between them.
- Correlations among three measures of organizational commitment are in general positive ranging between .416 and .590. All the three correlations are significantly positive depicting the construct validity of OCQ. Affective Commitment has correlated positively with Normative Commitment (.590, $p < .01$), and Continuance Commitment (.416, $p < .01$). Normative Commitment has marked significant positive association with Continuance Commitment (.505, $p < .01$). Hence, three measures of organizational commitment have shared substantial amount of variance among them.

Table 2: Inter Correlations Matrix (Females)

	Hope	Efficacy	Resilience	Optimism	AC	NC	CC
Hope	XX						
Efficacy	0.611	XX					
Resilience	0.477	0.513	XX				
Optimism	0.437	0.526	0.446	XX			
AC	0.278	0.348	0.209	0.329	XX		
NC	0.397	0.546	0.367	0.441	0.313	XX	
CC	0.051	0.057	0.068	0.288	0.013	0.113	XX

- Inter correlations among four measures of Psychological Capital are in general positive ranging from .446 to .611 with all being positive. Hope has correlated positively with Self- efficacy ($r = .611, p < .01$), Resilience ($r = .477, p < .01$), and Optimism ($r = .437, p < .01$). Self-efficacy has marked significant positive relationship with Resilience ($r = .513, p < .01$) and Optimism ($r = .526, p < .01$). Resilience and Optimism have correlated positively with each other with the coefficient of (.446, $p < .01$). Significant positive correlations among all the four measures of PsyCap hereby depict the construct validity of PsyCap Questionnaire and substantial amount of variance sharing among them.
- Correlations between four measures of PsyCap and three of Organizational Commitment are in general positive ranging between .051 and .546. Nine of 12 correlations are significant at or above .05 level of significance, all of which are positive. Hope has correlated positively with Affective Commitment ($r = .278, p < .01$) and Normative Commitment ($r = .397, p < .01$). Self-efficacy has marked significant positive association with Affective Commitment ($r = .348, p < .01$) and Normative Commitment ($r = .546, p < .01$). Resilience has borne out positive relationship with Affective Commitment ($r = .209, p < .01$) and Normative Commitment ($r = .367, p < .01$). Optimism has marked significant positive association with all the three measures of Organizational Commitment viz. Affective Commitment ($r = .329, p < .01$), Normative Commitment ($r = .441, p < .01$) and Continuous Commitment ($r = .288, p < .01$). Obtained correlations hereby depict that two types of measures have shared some amount of variance between them.
- Inter correlations among three measures of Organizational Commitment are in general positive ranging between .013 and .313. All the three correlations are significantly positive depicting the construct validity of OCQ and substantial amount of variance sharing among three components of OC. Affective Commitment has correlated positively with Normative Commitment ($r = .313, p < .01$), and Continuance Commitment ($r = .013, p < .01$). Normative Commitment has marked significant positive association with Continuance Commitment (.113, $p < .01$)

Findings and Discussion:

This paper confirms that impacts of PsyCap as antecedents of organizational commitment are almost similar to those in other organizational setups and work places. Implicitly, it implies that the school education system is bearing the common structural and functional features with other organizations, and human resource characteristics are equally important in effectiveness of educational organizations. Findings of the present study have depicted the significant positive relationship between psychological capital and organizational commitment. It is well established that psychological capital is developmental, so it implies that developing psychological capital, organizational commitment can be enhanced. So, the school education management/administration should consider the assessment of PsyCap among the candidates to be recruited as teachers.

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